

COLORIMETRIC ESTIMATION OF IRON WITH QUINALDINIC ACID. A CRITICAL STUDY

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The reagent quinaldinic acid has been utilised for the colorimetric estimation of iron visually from 0.4 p.p.m. to 130 p.p.m. and from 0.6 p.p.m. to 16 p.p.m. in a photoelectric colorimeter with a 20 mm. cell. The effect of various factors and of diverse ions on the coloured complex has been critically examined. The maximum absorption due to the coloured complex was found to be in the region of 515 μ .

The reagent quinaldinic acid was used by Ray and Bose (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1933, 95, 400) for the estimation of copper, cadmium, zinc, etc. They further found that the reagent could also be utilised for the colorimetric determination of ferrous iron. The colour of complex formed deepens with excess of cyanide, and this forms the basis for the colorimetric estimation of iron.

The purpose of the present investigation is to find out whether this reagent quinaldinic acid, which is cheaper and very easily prepared, can be recommended for the colorimetric determination of iron. With this idea a critical study of the various factors which may affect the formation of the coloured complex, including a study of the effect of varying concentrations of diverse ions usually encountered in routine analysis, has been made.

The maximum absorption due to the coloured system is found to be in the region of 515 μ . Though cyanide intensifies the colour, the maximum absorption region is not shifted either in presence of a large excess of it or of the reagent. Reducing agents, such as, hydroxylamine hydrochloride, hydrazine sulphate and hydrogen sulphide, are found to have no influence on the region of maximum absorption. In a cell of thickness 20 mm. and in a volume of 25 c. c., iron present should not be more than 0.4 mg., but during visual observations with a colorimeter of the Duboscq type, the concentration of iron may be increased to 4 mg. in a volume of 30 c. c. and the minimum amount of iron that can be accurately estimated is 2 γ in a volume of 5 c. c.

The function of cyanide is to give necessary alkalinity, but it seems probable that the cyanide also enters into the composition of the coloured compound.

EXPERIMENTAL

Apparatus and Solutions.—The optical density measurements were made with a Lumetron colorimeter of model 402 EF of Photovolt Corporation. Solutions for such measurements were taken in a corex glass cell of capacity 16 c. c. and of thickness 20 mm.

Chemicals used were all of the reagent quality. Standard solutions of iron were prepared from recrystallised Mohr salt (AnalaR) with water and a

few c.c. of concentrated H_2SO_4 , and the iron content of each solution was determined volumetrically by permanganate. Solutions weaker than those were prepared by dilution with water which was previously boiled to remove dissolved oxygen.

A solution of sodium quinaldinate was made from 1 g. of quinaldinic acid (prepared according to the method of Hammick, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 2882, and recrystallised) per 100 c.c. of the solution.

The effect of cyanide on the colour system was studied with a 2% solution of sodium cyanide, but in all other studies a 10% solution was used.

As reducing agents, a 5% solution of hydroxylamine hydrochloride, a 3% solution of hydrazine sulphate and a saturated solution of hydrogen sulphide at 30° were used.

Standard solutions of diverse ions were obtained from the nitrate or sulphate salts of cations and from the sodium or potassium salts of the anions. For studying the effect of mineral acids, 1% solutions of the acids were prepared.

Colour Reaction.—The reddish purple colour formed by the ferrous ion with the reagent showed maximum absorption in the region of $515 \mu\mu$. When sodium cyanide was added, after the addition of the reagent, to the ferrous ion, the intensity of colour increased, but the maximum absorption region remained the same even when a large excess of cyanide was used. Varying amounts of iron and the reagent had also no influence on the region of maximum absorption. Reducing agents such as, hydroxylamine hydrochloride, hydrazine sulphate, hydrogen sulphide, etc., were found to be without any influence on the maximum absorption region (curves in Fig. 1 show the effect).

FIG. 1.

I. Fe 0.1 mg., $NH_2OH.HCl$, 50 mg., ($NH_2-NH_2.H_2SO_4$, 30 mg.) ; reagent 10 mg., $NaCN$, 100 mg.

II. Fe 0.1 mg., reagent 10 mg., $NaCN$, 100 mg., H_2S -water, 4 c.c.

III. Fe 0.1 mg., reagent 10 mg., $NaCN$, 40 mg.

IV. Fe 0.2 mg., reagent 10 mg. (only in this case vol. of the soln. was made up with alcohol .

V. Fe 0.1 mg., reagent 1 mg., $NaCN$ 40 mg.

VI. Fe 0.04 mg., reagent 10 mg., $NaCN$, 20 mg.

VII. Fe 0.04 mg., reagent 0.4 mg., $NaCN$, 20 mg.

Ferrous ion forms with the reagent quinaldinic acid an inner metallic tetra-coordinated complex (Ray and Bose, *loc. cit.*). The increase in the intensity of the colour by the cyanide appears to be due to the formation of a hexa-co-ordinated complex of the type $\text{Na}_2[\text{Fe}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{NO}_2)_2(\text{CN})_2]$. The alkalinity caused by the alkali cyanide does not intensify the colour as the dilute solution of caustic soda or of sodium acetate has been found to decompose the complex with the precipitation of iron.

Effect of the Reagent, Cyanide and of Reducing Agents.—In order to study the effect of the different reagents on the coloured system at the wave-length of maximum absorption $515 \mu\mu$, varying amounts of the reagent were added keeping the concentration of iron and cyanide constant in a volume of 25 c.c. The effect of cyanide was similarly studied in the region of $515 \mu\mu$, with varying amounts of cyanide, while the concentrations of iron and the reagent were kept the same in the same volume of the solution. The results are graphically represented in curves I, II in Fig. 2. In the same way the influence of the reducing agents, such as hydroxylamine hydrochloride, hydrazine sulphate, and

FIG. 2

(Soln. contains 0.1 mg. of Fe)
Curves I and II refer respectively to reagent and cyanide.

FIG. 3

(Soln. contains 0.1 mg. Fe and 10 mg. reagent)
Curves I—III refer respectively to hydroxylamine hydrochloride, hydrazine sulphate and H_2S .

hydrogen sulphide was investigated and the results represented in curves I-III in Fig.3. The curves show that for the maximum colour development the reagent and cyanide required are respectively about 50 and 360 times the amount of the iron present, and the reducing agent hydroxylamine hydrochloride may be tolerated up to 750 times and the hydrazine sulphate up to 1800 times the amount of iron, without affecting the absorption.

That Beer's law is obeyed by the colour system is shown by the fact that straight lines are obtained when the optical densities at $515 \mu\mu$, for a number of solutions containing iron from 2×10^{-5} g. to 4×10^{-4} g. are plotted against the respective concentrations (Fig.4). The procedure followed was to add with stirring to the ferrous iron solution solutions of hydroxylamine hydrochloride or hydrazine sulphate, the reagent and the sodium cyanide, in the order as stated, and the volume of the solution was made up to 25 c.c. with water. The optical density of the solution thus obtained was measured. A few determinations were also made without the addition of the reducing agents. When the amount of iron is more than 0.4 mg. in 25 c.c. solution, the transmittancy is very small and hence measurements in that region have been avoided.

FIG. 4

- I. With reducing agent (hydroxylamine hydrochloride or hydrazine sulphate).
- II. Without reducing agent.

Some determinations were made by visual comparison in Klett's bio-colorimeter and the results obtained are given in Table I. The colour system was found to obey Beer's law through a long range of concentration studied up to 4 mg. in a volume of 30 c.c. Procedure followed was exactly the same as with the photo-electric colorimeter. The minimum amount of iron that can be estimated with accuracy is 27 in a volume of 5 c.c. If the iron concentration is over 4 mg., the colour developed in a volume of 30 c.c. is too intense for visual comparison.

TABLE I

Estimation of iron by visual comparison.

Iron taken (mg.)	0.002	0.005	0.02	0.04	0.08	0.16	0.2	0.4	0.6	1.0	3.0	4.0
Iron found (mg.)	0.002	0.0049	0.02	0.04	0.08	0.158	0.2	0.4	0.6	1.0	3.0	3.988
Difference (mg.)	Nil	0.0001	Nil	Nil	0.002	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	0.012

Stability of the Colour.—Full colour development is instantaneous after the addition of cyanide and it is independent of time interval for the addition of the reagents and the temperature of the solutions from 0° to 35°. The absorption due to the coloured system was found to remain constant for 1 hour when the amount of iron was 10⁻⁴g. in 25 c.c. and containing 1 c.c. each of hydroxylamine hydrochloride, reagent and the cyanide.

FIG. 5

FIG. 6

In order to determine the effect of different ions on the stability of the colour to the iron solution (0.1 mg. of iron) were added the ion whose effect

was to be determined and then hydroxylamine hydrochloride (1c.c.), the reagent (1 c.c.) and the cyanide (1 c.c.) in the order stated and the volume was made up to 25 c.c. (cf. Figs. 5-7). With the increase in the concentration of cyanide the effect due to other ions remained the same but those due to mineral acids decreased.

FIG. 7.

The following ions interfere when present at a concentration of in 25 c.c.—
 Ni^{++} 4 mg., Mn^{++} 4 mg., Cd^{++} 13 mg., Zn^{++} 0.9 mg., Pb^{++} 10 mg., PO_4^{--} ,
 0.9 mg., F⁻ 4 mg., citrate 0.3 mg., $\text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{O}_6$ 0.4 mg., HNO_3 40 mg.,
 H_2SO_4 70 mg., HCl, 80 mg.

The following ions are without any effect even at a concentration of 100 mg. in 25 c. c.— Mg^{++} , Ca^{++} , Ba^{++} , Sr^{++} , SO_4^{--} , NO_3^- , Cl^- .

Traces of copper or oxalate have a marked interfering effect.